

TECHNISCHE
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WIEN

Data management plan (DMP)

Extreme Poverty Calculation

EOSCSecretariat.eu

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1.0	14/05/2023	First version of DMP – created for start of project (deliverable xy)
2.0	14/05/2023	Second version of DMP – prepared for midterm review (deliverable xz)

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Project details

Contact person (responsible for data management and DMP)	Jeton Shehu, ORCID iD: 0009-0004-6905-6966
Contributors	Jeton Shehu, ORCID iD: 0009-0004-6905-6966, Researcher
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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- European Commission's document on Ethics and Data Protection: https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/5_h2020_ethics_and_data_protection.pdf
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Country Class Group	Structured text		100 MB	no

Reused datasets

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Country Table 1.9\$	10.5281/zenodo.7933483		no
R2	Data World Bank Indicators	10.5281/zenodo.7935056		no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data will be derived from the World Bank dataset, utilizing Jupyter Notebook and Python libraries to explore and generate new data.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The datasets are referenced and utilized within the Jupyter Notebook execution, accompanied by explanations of each method's role in terms of data pre-processing and handling. The source code is at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7935075>

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

R1 (Country Table 1.9\$), R2 (Data World Bank Indicators), P1 (Country Class Group) will be stored in Zenodo. Due to the unavailability of the dataset containing countries and their values at the extreme poverty line (R1) online, it became necessary to upload it to the Zenodo repository. On the other hand, the R2 dataset comprises numerous indicators, each with its own description defining the data it represents. These indicators can be accessed online on <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator?tab=all> by searching for specific indicators and exploring their corresponding metadata. The datasets in the R2 repository is a combination of this indicators.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien (Verena Dolovai), and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open			Zenodo		CC BY 4.0

The specific DOI for the dataset is: 10.5281/zenodo.7935056

The repositories used in this project are described in the following paragraph:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results.
<https://zenodo.org/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: No Specific Tools

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	Zenodo	10 years	Students and general public

Overview of (unpublished) data that will be deleted:

dataset ID	kind/name of data	date of deletion	reason for deletion	responsible person

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The [PI / data officer XY] will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained. The lead country researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

Additional description (if required):